

Oral presentation

BRACE MAP, a proposal for a new classification of braces

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Background

The existing classification of braces considers only the anatomical spinal section involved (C: cervical; T: thoracic; L: lumbar; S: sacral; Orthosis). The lack of a more detailed classification restricts the ability to distinguish between the braces and to provide a common reference between the conservative treatment experts.

Aim

To propose and to verify a new classification of braces.

Methods

Theoretical development of a classification and an application to 13 different braces (Boston, Charleston, Cheneau 2000, Lapadula, Lyonese, Maguelone, Milwaukee, PASB, Providence, Sforzesco, Sibilla, SpineCor, Triac).

Classification

We considered the following items (acronym BRACE MAP): Building, Rigidity, Anatomical classification, Construction of the Envelope, Mechanism of Action, Plane of action. Each item is composed by 2 to 7 classificatory elements defined using one or maximum two letters, so that from the classification it is possible to come back to the brace characteristics (e.g. SpineCor is classified as CpETAM3, that means Custom positioning, Elastic, TLSO, Asymmetric, Movement principle, 3D correction).

Results

Out of the 13 braces considered, BRACE MAP did provide the ability to differentiate between the braces except for two types.

Conclusion

This first proposal needs to be refined through Consensus during the meeting; nevertheless, it appears to be useful in distinguishing between the existing braces.